

Syntheses of Some 2,3-Dihydro-2-hydroxy-1,5-benzothiazepines

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The reaction of *p*-bromobenzoylacetone with 2-aminobenzenethiols in pyridine or dimethylsulphoxide afforded 1,5-benzothiazepines.

RECENTLY we reported the syntheses of 1,5-benzothiazepines by reacting 2-aminobenzenethiols with α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds^{1,2}. In the present communication, we have used a 1,3-diketone instead of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds for the syntheses of 1,5-benzothiazepines.

2-Aminobenzenethiols (1a-g) when heated with *p*-bromobenzoylacetone in DMSO or pyridine at 145–50°, the reaction mixture showed the colour change from pale-yellow to deep red. The removal of the solvent under reduced pressure afforded solids which on crystallisation with methanol gave invariably crystalline orange needles. Method using pyridine gave better yield. No solid was obtained in neutral or acidic medium.

The structure of compound 3 was characterised by elemental, ir and pmr analyses.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G by using benzene-ethanol-ammonia (7:2:1) as solvent system. Microestimations for nitrogen were carried out in Microanalytical Division, Melbourne, Australia. The ir spectra were taken in KBr pallets on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 577 spectrometer. Pmr spectra (δ scale) were recorded in TFA at 60 MHz on a R12B Perkin-Elmer spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

2,3-Dihydro-2-hydroxy-2-(p-bromophenyl)-4-methyl-1,5-benzothiazepine (3a): A mixture of 2-aminobenzenethiol (1.25 g, 0.01 mol), *p*-bromobenzoylacetone (2.41 g, 0.01 mol) and pyridine (10.0 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The colour of the reaction mixture turned yellowish orange from pale-yellow. It was poured on to crushed ice with stirring. The solid thus obtained, was filtered, dried and crystallised from methanol giving orange needles (2.26 g, 64%), m.p. 194° (Found: N, 3.92. C₁₆H₁₄NOSBr requires: N, 4.00%), R_f 0.69; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 370, 1 460 (CH₃ bending), 1 555 ($\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-C}}$), 3 275, 3 450–500 (ν_{OH} and ν_{NH}); δ 1.95 (3H, s, CH₃) and 4.68 (1H, s, H₃C–C=CH)

Similarly, 3b-g were prepared by using DMSO in place of pyridine and their physical data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF 8-SUBSTITUTED-2,3-DIHYDRO-2-HYDROXY-2-(4-BROMOPHENYL)-4-METHYL-1,5-BENZOTHAZEPINE (3a-g)

Compd.	M.p.	R _f	Yield %	Mol. formula	Mol. wt.	Analysis% N : Found/(Calcd.)
3b	220	0.76	62	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NOSFBr	366	3.70 (3.82)
3c	215	0.66	59	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NOSClBr	382.5	3.74 (3.68)
3d	209	0.75	62	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NOSBr ₂	427	3.46 (3.27)
3e	208	0.71	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ NOSBr	362	3.69 (3.86)
3f	226	0.68	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ NO ₂ SBr	378	3.65 (3.70)
3g	230	0.73	57	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ NO ₂ SBr	392	3.48 (3.57)

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